

Factors Influencing Students' Satisfaction and Persistence in Open and Distance Learning Programs: Perspectives from Learners in Selected NOUN Centres in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the factors influencing students' satisfaction and persistence in the Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programs at the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN). Using a mixed-methods research design, 155 respondents from 13 NOUN study centers in Abuja and Lagos were sampled through simple random sampling. The sample size was determined with the finite population correction (FPC), an adjusted version of the Cochran formula. A structured survey questionnaire incorporating Likert-scale and open-ended questions was used to collect data from participants. Results show positive perceptions, with high satisfaction levels in areas such as course content, academic standards, flexibility, and technical support. Students also prioritize intrinsic motivation, personal goals, prior educational experiences, and time management in maintaining their engagement. However, key areas for improvement include course delivery methods, feedback systems, instructor interaction, and interactive opportunities. A small portion of respondents reported challenges like limited face-to-face interaction, insufficient feedback, lack of social support, and occasional dissatisfaction with study center services. These findings highlight the need to improve ODL instructional design and support services to better serve diverse learner needs. The study concludes that, although NOUN's ODL programs have significantly increased educational access across Nigeria, targeted enhancements in infrastructure, teaching methods, and student support are crucial for improving overall effectiveness and student satisfaction. Recommendations include increasing delivery flexibility, enhancing instructor engagement, upgrading technical support, and promoting peer support networks.

Keywords: *National Open University of Nigeria, Open and Distance Learning (ODL), Student Satisfaction, Student Persistence, Course Delivery*

Introduction

Open and distance learning (ODL) programs have gained significant popularity in recent years due to their flexibility and accessibility. These programs provide opportunities for individuals to pursue higher education without the constraints of traditional classroom-based learning. The National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) is one such institution that offers ODL programs to a diverse range of learners. However, the success of these programs depends on various factors that influence student satisfaction and persistence. Norhayat, Omar, Irda, and Farah (2021) reported that student satisfaction is an essential element to enhance the learning process, especially in the ODL mode. They posit that while applying the ODL, classes are conducted via a blend of asynchronous (without real-time interaction) and synchronous (real-time interaction) sessions.

Several studies have investigated the factors influencing student satisfaction and persistence in ODL programs. Studies like Ahmad (2024) identified key factors, such as academic quality, student support services, campus environment, technological integration, and administrative efficiency, influencing students' satisfaction and persistence in ODL programs. In another study, Itasanmi and Oni (2019) proved that there is a significant relationship between teaching and learning experience, educational resources, technical support and infrastructure, and general satisfaction of students in ODL programmes. Although Adekambi (2019) believes that Information quality, system quality, and service quality were not significant predictors of students' satisfaction, except with the Email, where information and service quality influenced overall satisfaction. Other key factors identified influencing student satisfaction and persistence in ODL programs are the quality of instructional materials and resources provided to learners. In another study, Au, Li, and Wong (2018) mentioned that the factors influencing students' satisfaction and persistence in open and distance learning programs are dependent on the various categories of students, as satisfaction and capacity are dependent on students' level of academic comprehension. Also, research suggests that learners who perceive the instructional materials as relevant, engaging, and of high quality are more likely to be satisfied and persist in their studies (Bates, 2005; Moore & Kearsley, 2011; Raimi & Adias, 2018). Therefore, institutions like NOUN need to ensure that their instructional materials meet the needs and expectations of their learners.

Another important factor that influences student satisfaction and persistence is the level of support and interaction provided by the institution. Learners in ODL programs often face challenges related to isolation and a lack of guidance. Therefore, institutions need to establish effective support systems, such as online forums, virtual classrooms, and academic advisors, to address these challenges and enhance learner satisfaction and persistence (Tait, 2018; Daniel, 2012). Furthermore, the role of technology in ODL programs cannot be overlooked. Technology plays a crucial role in facilitating communication, collaboration, and access to learning resources. Learners who have access to reliable and user-friendly technological tools are more likely to be satisfied and persist in their studies (Keegan, 2013). Therefore, institutions like NOUN need to invest in technological infrastructure and provide adequate training and support to learners to ensure their satisfaction and persistence.

Alongside these factors, learner characteristics and motivations significantly influence satisfaction and persistence in Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programs. Studies indicate that learners with strong self-regulation, intrinsic motivation, and a clear sense of their academic goals are more likely to remain engaged and satisfied with their studies (Garrison & Cleveland-Innes, 2005; Tinto, 1993). As such, institutions need to take these attributes into account when designing and implementing ODL programs

Understanding the factors that contribute to student satisfaction and persistence in ODL programs is crucial for institutions like NOUN to enhance the quality of education and improve student outcomes. This academic

introduction aims to explore these factors from the perspectives of NOUN learners. It will provide an overview of the current literature on student satisfaction and persistence in ODL programs, highlight the significance of the study, and outline the research objectives and methodology. This research will therefore identify the key factors that contribute to students' satisfaction in NOUN's ODL programs. It will also examine the factors influencing students' persistence in NOUN's ODL programs. Understand the perspectives of NOUN students regarding the factors that contribute to student satisfaction in NOUN's ODL program. The study will also determine if the level of support and interaction provided by the institution influences student satisfaction in NOUN's ODL programs. Finally, examine the extent to which students' characteristics and motivations influence student persistence in NOUN's ODL programs?

Conceptual and Theoretical Framework

Open and Distance Learning (ODL) program in Nigeria

Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programs in Nigeria have become an essential component of the country's educational system, particularly in addressing the challenge of access to quality higher education. The National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN), established in 1983, is the primary institution offering ODL programs, which have enabled thousands of Nigerians to pursue higher education despite geographical and socio-economic barriers (Ogunyemi, 2007). ODL in Nigeria has provided an avenue for non-traditional students such as working adults, those in rural areas, and individuals with financial constraints to access education through flexible learning methods. The use of multimedia platforms, such as online courses, audio-visual materials, and print resources, has made ODL programs highly adaptable to the needs of diverse learners (Nwosu, 2017). These programs allow students to learn at their own pace, making it especially beneficial for those who are unable to attend conventional institutions due to work or family responsibilities (Olakulehin, 2007). In particular, the advancement of technology and the increasing availability of the internet has expanded the reach and effectiveness of ODL in Nigeria (Aderinoye, 2004).

However, several challenges hinder the full effectiveness of ODL programs in Nigeria. Issues such as poor internet connectivity, inadequate infrastructure, and a lack of technical training for both students and instructors remain barriers to the success of ODL (Adebayo & Ajayi, 2015). Moreover, there are concerns about the quality of education in ODL programs, with some skeptics arguing that the lack of face-to-face interaction may reduce the overall learning experience (Ali, 2006). Research has shown that there are also concerns regarding the credibility and recognition of ODL qualifications in the labor market, which may affect the motivation of some prospective students (Iruonagbe, 2016). Nevertheless, studies have emphasized that ODL has the potential to address the growing demand for education in Nigeria. It also contributes to addressing educational inequalities and improving access to higher education for marginalized populations (Ogunyemi, 2007). A critical review of ODL programs in

Nigeria indicates that while there is progress, a more robust framework is needed to ensure that technological, administrative, and pedagogical improvements continue to support the growth of ODL (Oyesomi & Ogunlade, 2018).

Open and Distance Learning (ODL) and students' satisfaction

The Open and Distance Learning (ODL) system has gained significant popularity in Nigeria due to its ability to offer flexible and accessible education to a diverse range of students. The National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN), Nigeria's largest provider of ODL, plays a key role in facilitating higher education for those who may otherwise be excluded due to geographical, economic, or social barriers. Despite the rapid growth of ODL programs, students' satisfaction with these programs remains a critical issue in assessing their effectiveness. ODL programs in Nigeria offer a blend of online learning and traditional correspondence methods, including multimedia materials, online discussion forums, and printed study materials. These programs have particularly benefited students in remote or rural areas, working professionals, and adults with family responsibilities who may find it difficult to commit to full-time on-campus education. ODL programs offer flexibility, allowing students to learn at their own pace and on their schedule, a crucial factor given Nigeria's high population and diverse socio-economic challenges (Nwosu, 2017).

The use of technology is a defining feature of ODL in Nigeria. However, access to stable internet and technology infrastructure remains a challenge. While urban areas tend to benefit from better connectivity, students in rural areas often experience difficulties accessing online resources (Ogunyemi, 2007). Additionally, the lack of face-to-face interaction with lecturers and peers has led to concerns about the development of a strong learning community and the overall quality of education. Student satisfaction in ODL programs is a multidimensional concept, encompassing factors such as academic support, course content, delivery methods, access to technology, and institutional support. Research on student satisfaction in ODL programs in Nigeria suggests a mixed response, with students expressing both positive and negative experiences.

The Positive Aspects of ODL reflect its:

Flexibility and Accessibility: A primary advantage of ODL programs is the flexibility they offer. Students can balance education with work and family commitments. For many, ODL represents an opportunity to access higher education that may not have been available through traditional means (Aderinoye, 2004). This aspect of ODL has been crucial for adult learners who are already part of the workforce or live in distant areas.

Cost-Effectiveness: ODL programs are generally more affordable than traditional on-campus programs. With the rising cost of education in Nigeria, ODL provides an economical alternative for many students who may not be able to afford the high fees associated with conventional education (Iruonagbe, 2016).

Personalized Learning: The ability to learn at one's own pace, coupled with access to a variety of resources, allows for more personalized learning. This flexibility appeals to students who learn better through independent study and self-regulation (Olakulehin, 2007).

Theoretical Frameworks

Expectation-Confirmation Theory (ECT)

Developed by Oliver (1980), the hypothesis is a popular paradigm for researching customer satisfaction. According to ECT, the degree to which students' initial expectations regarding the educational experience are met or exceeded affects their level of satisfaction. High satisfaction is likely to result from expectations being realised; low satisfaction results from expectations not being satisfied. This is relevant to the ODL programme, as students register with certain expectations and a particular mindset, and they continually evaluate whether their experiences match their expectations. Dissatisfaction can arise from negative confirmations, yet increased satisfaction is the consequence of positive confirmations.

Tinto's Model of Student Retention

Tinto's Model of Student Retention (1993) stressed the importance of academic and social integration in student persistence. Here, students are more likely to persist in their studies if they feel academically and socially connected to their educational institution. In ODL programs, academic integration involves engagement with course materials, interaction with instructors, and academic performance, which are crucial factors. Social integration refers to students' sense of belonging and community within the educational environment, fostered through online discussions, peer collaborations, and virtual social activities.

Bean and Metzner's Model of Non-Traditional Student Attrition

The Bean and Metzner's model of non-traditional student attrition, developed by Bean and Metzner (1985), highlights the different experiences and challenges non-traditional students face. Termed external factors, the model stressed the impact of these external factors, such as financial pressures, family responsibilities, work commitments, institutional support, quality of education, etc. Understanding how financial, familial, occupational pressures, academic advising, counselling, and technological assistance affect ODL students' persistence is critical to attaining Student satisfaction

Methodology

This study adopted a mixed-methods research design to collect both quantitative and qualitative data. Mixed methods research is important in this research as it enhances the breadth, depth, and accuracy of findings, making it a powerful approach for addressing multifaceted research questions and generating richer, more actionable

insights. A total of 260 respondents were purposively selected from 13 NOUN centres in Abuja and Lagos, with 20 students drawn from each centre. The centres were chosen based on their geographic spread and accessibility and include Abuja Model Study Centre, NOUN Special Study Centre, National Union of Road Transport Workers (NURTW), Special Study Centre, for Nigerian Police Force, NOUN Special Study Centre, Nigerian Security and Civil Defense Corps (NSCDC), NOUN Wuse II Study Centre, Abuja, NOUN Special Study Centre, Kuje Prisons, Special Study Centre Immigration, Gwagwalada, Abuja, Badagry Study Centre, Lagos Study Centre, McCarthy Study Centre, Lagos Mainland Study Centre, NOUN Special Study Centre Nigeria Prisons KiriKiri Maximum Prisons (Male & Female) and Ikorodu Study Centre. The study covered eight faculties: Agricultural Sciences, Arts, Education, Health Sciences, Law, Management, Science, and Social Sciences. A structured survey questionnaire using a Likert scale and open-ended questions was administered to gather data on student satisfaction and persistence. Key focus areas included instructional materials, learner support systems, technology access, and learner motivation. To complement the survey, semi-structured in-depth interviews were conducted with selected respondents to gain a deeper understanding of their learning experiences. This combination of methods provided a holistic understanding of the factors influencing students’ satisfaction and persistence in open and distance learning at NOUN. The study population is 260; however, a representative sample size of one hundred and fifty-five (155) respondents was randomly sampled using the simple random sampling technique for the study. The sample size from the universal population (260) was based on the selected NOUN Centres in Abuja and Lagos, Nigeria.

Results and Discussion

Factors contributing to student satisfaction in the Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programs

Table 1: Factors contributing to student satisfaction in the Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programs

Factors	Frequency (%)			
	SA	A	D	SD
1. <i>To what extent do you agree that the course in NOUN's ODL programs meets your academic needs?</i>	40(25.81)	70(45.16)	30(19.35)	15(9.67)
2. <i>To what extent do you agree that the course content in NOUN's ODL programs meets your academic needs?</i>	50(32.26)	65(41.93)	30(19.35)	10(6.45)
3. <i>To what extent do you agree that the course content delivery mode by academics in NOUN's ODL programs meets your academic needs?</i>	60(38.71)	50(32.26)	30(19.35)	15(9.67)
4. <i>To what extent do you agree that the course content standards in NOUN's ODL programs meets your academic needs?</i>	40(25.81)	70(45.16)	30(19.35)	15(9.67)

A survey assessing how well NOUN’s ODL programs meet academic needs shows generally positive feedback, with course content and standards receiving the highest approval (45.16% agreement). This supports studies emphasizing the role of structured content and high standards in ODL effectiveness (Moore & Kearsley, 2011; Simonson et al., 2019). The alignment of course materials with learners’ expectations further reinforces the value of curriculum design in distance education. In contrast, 32.26% agreed that the delivery mode meets their academic needs—slightly lower than content ratings. However, 38.71% strongly agreed, the highest strong agreement rate across the questions. This reflects a preference for flexible delivery, despite known challenges like tech issues and limited interaction (Harrison, 2013; Anderson, 2015; Garrison & Kanuka, 2004). Also, 25.81% strongly agreed that the content met their needs, confirming general curriculum satisfaction. However, some disagreement across questions shows that not all needs are met. Strong disagreement (6.45% for content, 9.67% for delivery) signals dissatisfaction, echoing research on the importance of addressing both content and delivery challenges in ODL (Perry et al., 2012; Hood & Littlejohn, 2017). Overall, most respondents agree or strongly agree that NOUN’s ODL programs meet academic needs. This affirms the importance of well-managed programs that combine quality content, flexible delivery, and strong learner support, as suggested by Perraton (2000), to enhance learning outcomes and satisfaction.

Table 2: Factors that influence student persistence in the Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programs

<i>Factors</i>	<i>Frequency (%)</i>			
	SA	A	D	SD
1. <i>To what extent do you agree that your personal goals and motivations significantly influence your persistence in NOUN's ODL programs?</i>	50(32.26)	80(51.61)	15(9.68)	10(6.45)
2. <i>How would you rate the level of support you receive from family and peers in your pursuit of studies at NOUN?</i>	VH	H	L	VL
3. <i>To what extent do you feel that the quality of instructions and engagement with course materials impact your decision to continue in the program?</i>	30(19.35)	85(54.84)	30(19.35)	10(6.45)
	VM	M	S	NA
4. <i>How satisfied are you with accessing your study centre</i>	60(38.71)	60(38.71)	20(12.90)	15(9.68)
5. <i>How satisfied are you with the fees paid for the programme?</i>	VS	S	D	VD
6. <i>How satisfied are you with the flexibility of NOUN's ODL programs in helping you manage your time effectively?</i>	40(25.81)	85(54.84)	20(12.90)	10 (6.45)
	40(25.81)	80(51.61)	20(12.90)	15(9.68)
	50(32.26)	75(48.39)	20(12.90)	10(6.45)

A significant majority (83.87%) of respondents either strongly agree (32.26%) or agree (51.61%) that personal goals and motivations greatly influence their persistence in NOUN’s Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programs.

This supports the self-determination theory, which emphasizes the importance of intrinsic motivation and goal-setting in educational success (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Tinto, 2012). Conversely, 16.13% either disagree (9.68%) or strongly disagree (6.45%), possibly due to external barriers like financial or family pressures (Artino, 2012). In terms of social support, 74.19% of respondents reported receiving high (54.84%) or very high (19.35%) support from family and peers, indicating the strong role of social networks in academic persistence. This aligns with findings by Garrison et al. (2010), which highlight the positive impact of social support on motivation and retention in ODL. However, 25.81% of students experienced low (19.35%) or very low (6.45%) support, a concern linked to increased dropout rates and academic challenges (Vaughan, 2014).

The majority of respondents (77.42%) (either very much (38.71%) or moderately (38.71%)) believe that the quality of instruction and course engagement significantly influences their decision to continue with the program. This highlights the importance of course design and delivery in retention, which is supported by research, linking instructional quality to student success in ODL (Moore & Kearsley, 2011; Garrison & Akyol, 2013). Only 22.58% feel the impact is minimal or none. Most students find the content engaging, reinforcing its role in their continued participation.

A majority of respondents (80.65%) are satisfied (54.84%) or very satisfied (25.81%) with access to study centers, suggesting this is not a major issue for most. This aligns with research highlighting the role of physical infrastructure in supporting learning and community in ODL (Nunan & Stubbins, 2005). However, 19.35% expressed dissatisfaction, indicating room for improvement. The uneven access may reflect regional disparities, which can affect students' overall experience.

A majority (77.42%) of respondents are satisfied with the program fees, suggesting they find the cost reasonable. This supports research linking cost-benefit perceptions to satisfaction in ODL (Larsen & Lewis, 2007). However, 22.58% are dissatisfied, pointing to affordability concerns. These concerns may be more pronounced among economically disadvantaged students (Choy, 2002). Addressing this could improve overall satisfaction and retention.

A majority (80.65%) of respondents are satisfied with the flexibility of NOUN's ODL programs, highlighting its value for time management. This aligns with research citing flexibility as a key benefit for non-traditional learners (Allen & Seaman, 2013; Bernard et al., 2004). However, 19.35% expressed dissatisfaction, suggesting the flexibility may not meet all students' needs. This points to potential gaps in adapting the program to diverse learner circumstances (Feng, 2015).

Table 3: Factors that contribute to student personal satisfaction in NOUN's Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programs

<i>Factors</i>	<i>Frequency (%)</i>			
	VM	M	S	NA
1. <i>To what extent do you feel that the availability of technical support positively impacts your learning experience in NOUN's ODL programs?</i>	80(51.61)	50(32.26)	15(9.68)	10(6.45)
2. <i>How satisfied are you with the communication and responsiveness of instructors in NOUN's ODL programs?</i>	VS	S	D	SD
	50(32.25)	80(51.61)	15(9.68)	10(6.45)
3. <i>How would you rate your overall satisfaction with your learning experience in NOUN's ODL programs?</i>	60(38.71)	75(48.38)	15(9.68)	5(3.23)

A significant majority (83.87%) of respondents believe technical support positively impacts their learning, with 51.61% strongly agreeing and 32.26% moderately agreeing. This underscores the importance of technical assistance in ODL, consistent with past studies (Perraton, 2000; O'Neill, 2012). However, 16.13% feel the impact is minimal, suggesting either low need or unmet expectations. This aligns with research showing technical support effectiveness varies with users' competencies and perceived quality (Harris & Rea, 2009; McConnell, 2012).

Similarly, 83.87% of respondents are satisfied with instructor communication and responsiveness, 32.26% very satisfied, and 51.61% satisfied. This supports findings that timely communication enhances satisfaction and retention in ODL (Moore & Kearsley, 2011; Swan, 2003). Still, 16.13% report dissatisfaction, highlighting the need for improvement. Research confirms that instructor presence reduces isolation and improves learning (Anderson, 2003; Garrison & Vaughan, 2008).

A majority (87.10%) report overall satisfaction with their NOUN ODL experience—38.71% very satisfied, 48.39% satisfied. This indicates the program meets most students' expectations, reflecting research linking satisfaction to course design, interaction, and resources (Shah, 2018; Bernard et al., 2004). However, 12.90% are dissatisfied, pointing to possible issues like instructional design gaps or insufficient support (Lee, 2014; Tinto, 2012). While most students find technical support beneficial, a small group sees limited value, emphasizing the need for adaptable support systems tailored to diverse learner needs (Garrison et al., 2010). Instructor communication is well-rated overall, though some students note lapses. Studies show consistent engagement is critical for success in online learning (Bawa, 2016). Overall satisfaction is strong, but minor dissatisfaction suggests areas for improvement—especially in feedback, clarity, and support (Palloff & Pratt, 2013).

Table 4: Level of support and interaction provided by the institution influences student satisfaction in NOUN's Open and Distance Learning (ODL) programs

No	Support Level	Frequency (%)			
		SA	A	D	SD
5	To what extent do you agree that the student counsellor support services positively influence your satisfaction with the ODL programs?	60 (38.71%)	70 (45.16%)	15 (9.68%)	10 (6.45%)
		SA	A	D	SD
6	To what extent do you agree that the study centre desk officers and staff services positively influence your satisfaction with the ODL programs?	55 (35.48%)	75 (48.39%)	15 (9.68%)	10 (6.45%)
		VM	M	S	NA
7	To what extent do you feel that the University websites and portals are user-friendly and impact your satisfaction with the program?	50 (32.26%)	70 (45.16%)	25 (16.13%)	10 (6.45%)
		VS	S	D	VD
8	How would you rate your satisfaction with the feedback mechanisms in place for assessing your performance and progress in NOUN's ODL programs?	45 (29.03%)	80 (51.61%)	20 (12.90%)	10 (6.45%)
		VS	S	D	VD
9	How satisfied are you with the opportunities for interaction and collaboration with fellow students in NOUN's ODL programs?	40 (25.81%)	85 (54.84%)	20 (12.90%)	10 (6.45%)

A majority (83.87%) of respondents believe student counseling services positively impact their satisfaction, with 38.71% strongly agreeing and 45.16% agreeing. This supports research highlighting the role of academic support in ODL retention and satisfaction (Simpson, 2002; Kember, 1995). However, 16.13% disagree, suggesting some students find the support ineffective. Studies show counseling is most impactful when tailored to individual needs (Tinto, 2012; Bean, 1980). Similarly, 83.87% agree that desk officers and staff at study centres contribute to satisfaction, 35.48% strongly and 48.39% moderately. This aligns with literature on the value of in-person support in ODL (Garrison & Vaughan, 2008; Bernard et al., 2004). Yet, 16.13% express dissatisfaction, pointing to possible gaps in service delivery, echoing findings about the impact of delayed or unclear administrative support (Githens, 2007).

About 77.42% of students find the university websites and portals useful, while 22.58% report limited usefulness. This suggests room to enhance digital platforms for broader usability. Research underscores the importance of intuitive online systems in boosting engagement and satisfaction in ODL programs (Horton, 2011; Allen & Seaman, 2013). A strong majority (80.64%) are satisfied with the feedback mechanisms, reinforcing the importance of timely, constructive feedback in learning (Nicol & Macfarlane-Dick, 2006; Hattie & Timperley, 2007). However, 19.35% are dissatisfied, suggesting a need for more precise, actionable, and clear feedback (Carless, 2015).

Most respondents (80.65%) are satisfied with interaction and collaboration opportunities, while 19.35% are not. This highlights a need to expand student interaction options. Research shows that collaborative projects and forums reduce isolation and improve learning in ODL environments (Garrison et al., 2010; McConnell, 2012).

Table 5: Extent to which students’ characteristics and motivations influence student persistence in NOUN's ODL programs

<i>Items</i>	<i>Frequency (%)</i>			
1. <i>To what extent do you agree that your intrinsic motivation (e.g., personal interest in learning) significantly influences your persistence in NOUN's ODL programs?</i>	SA	A	D	SD
	65(41.94)	70(45.16)	15(9.68)	5(3.23)
2. <i>How would you rate the impact of your prior educational experiences on your decision to continue your studies in NOUN's ODL programs?</i>	SI	MI	SI	II
	80(51.61)	55(35.48)	15(9.68)	5(3.23)
3. <i>To what extent do you feel that your time management skills influence your ability to persist in your studies at NOUN?</i>	VM	M	S	NA
	75(48.39)	50(32.26)	20(12.90)	10(6.45)
4. <i>How satisfied are you with your personal goal orientation (e.g., clear career objectives) in terms of its influence on your persistence in the program?</i>	VS	S	D	VD
	60(38.71)	75(48.39)	15(9.68)	5(3)

87.10% of students believe intrinsic motivation plays a key role in their persistence, with 41.94% strongly agreeing. This supports self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000), which emphasizes intrinsic motivation as a key driver of academic engagement. Only 12.90% disagree, indicating that personal interest in learning is a significant motivator for most students (Vallerand et al., 1992; Schunk et al., 2008). 87.10% of students feel their prior educational experiences positively impact their decision to continue studying, with 41.61% reporting a significant impact. Previous academic experiences contribute to student confidence and persistence (Tinto, 1993; Bandura,

1997). However, 12.90% feel prior education has little to no impact, suggesting that for some students, past experiences are less influential.

80.65% of students agree that time management influences their persistence, with 48.39% rating it highly. Effective time management is critical for balancing academic and personal commitments (Britton & Tesser, 1991). However, 19.35% feel time management has little impact, indicating challenges in balancing responsibilities, which can lead to stress and academic underperformance (Artino, 2009; Zimmerman, 2000). 87.10% of students are satisfied with how their personal goals influence persistence, with 38.71% very satisfied. Clear goals are a strong predictor of persistence (Locke & Latham, 2002), motivating students to continue their studies (Schunk et al., 2008). However, 12.90% are dissatisfied, suggesting that some students may lack clear goals or struggle to use them effectively, which can affect persistence (Tinto, 1997).

Conclusion

The analysis of students' enrollment in NOUNs Open and Distant Learning (ODL) programs indicates a predominantly favourable response alongside identifiable areas for improvement. The majority of participants agreed that the course material and academic standards align with their requirements. However, some respondents believe that delivery methods, including technological impediments and the lack of face-to-face interaction, Flexibility offered, and the availability of technical support, are widely valued, although there is potential for further improvements.

Support from family and peers, high-quality instruction, and active course engagement are critical for students' retention, although some learners encounter difficulties. Additionally, satisfaction levels regarding study centres, tuition fees, feedback system, and opportunities for interaction are notably high. Although a small percentage of respondents perceive opportunities for improvements, particularly in the quality of feedback and engagement. Factors such as intrinsic motivation, previous educational background, and effective time management play a significant role in influencing students' persistence.

Recommendations

- i. Enhance flexibility in delivery methods through asynchronous options and diversified platforms.
- ii. Boost social support via peer networks and mentorship programs.
- iii. Improve feedback by making it clearer, timelier, and actionable.
- iv. Increase instructor engagement through frequent communication and online teaching training.
- v. Strengthen technical support and upgrade platform usability for a better learning experience.

References

- Adebayo, F. A., & Ajayi, A. O. (2015). Open and distance learning in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 3(10), 335–342.
- Adekambi, J. O. (2019). E-learning delivery methods: Predictors of satisfaction by students of Nigerian universities. *Asian Review of Social Science*, 8(3), 8–14. <https://doi.org/10.51983/arss-2019.8.3.1604>
- Aderinoye, R. A. (2004). The role of open and distance learning in national development. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Administration and Planning*, 4(2), 23–37.
- Ahmad, M. A. (2025). Assessing the factors influencing students' satisfaction in Nigerian tertiary institutions: A principal component analysis approach. In B. Alareeni & I. Elgedawy (Eds.), *Opportunities and risks in AI for business development* (Vol. 546). Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-65207-3_35
- Ali, M. (2006). Open and distance learning in Nigeria: The challenges of the 21st century. *International Journal of Education and Development using Information and Communication Technology (IJEDICT)*, 2(3), 36–50.
- Allen, I. E., & Seaman, J. (2013). *Changing course: Ten years of tracking online education in the United States*. Babson Survey Research Group.
- Anderson, T. (2003). Getting the mix right again: An updated and theoretical rationale for interaction. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 4(2), 1–14.
- Anderson, T. (2015). *Theories for learning with emerging technologies*. Routledge.
- Artino, A. R. (2009). Promoting academic motivation and self-regulation in online learning environments. In M. G. Moore (Ed.), *Handbook of distance education* (3rd ed., pp. 367–380). Routledge.
- Artino, A. R. (2012). Motivational design for online learning: A case study. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 13(3), 72–89.
- Au, O. T. S., Li, K., & Wong, T. M. (2019). Student persistence in open and distance learning: Success factors and challenges. *Asian Association of Open Universities Journal*, 13(2), 191–202.
- Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. Macmillan.
- Bates, A. T. (2005). *Technology, e-learning and distance education*. Routledge.
- Bawa, P. (2016). Retention in online courses: Exploring issues and solutions—A literature review. *Sage Open*, 6(1), 2158244015621777.
- Bean, J. P. (1980). Dropouts and turnover: The synthesis and test of a causal model of student attrition. *Research in Higher Education*, 12, 155–187.
- Bernard, R. M., Abrami, P. C., Borokhovski, E., Wozney, L., Walseth, P. A., & Noroozi, O. (2004). A meta-analysis of research on online learning: A perspective from modern distance education. *Review of Educational Research*, 74(3), 377–415.
- Britton, B. K., & Tesser, A. (1991). Effects of time-management practices on college grades. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 83(3), 405–410.
- Carless, D. (2015). Explanations and consequences: Feedback in higher education. *Studies in Higher Education*, 40(2), 235–252.
- Choy, S. P. (2002). *Access and persistence of undergraduates: First-generation students*. U.S. Department of Education, National Center for Education Statistics.
- Daniel, J. (2012). *Sampling essentials: Practical guidelines for making sampling choices*. Sage Publications.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227–268.
- Feng, J. (2015). Distance education in China: Opportunities and challenges. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(30), 85–91.
- Garrison, D. R., & Akyol, Z. (2013). The community of inquiry theory ten years later: Update to the most influential model in the world of online learning. *Internet and Higher Education*, 18, 57–61.
- Garrison, D. R., & Cleveland-Innes, M. (2005). Facilitating cognitive presence in online learning: Interaction is not enough. *American Journal of Distance Education*, 19, 133–14.
- Garrison, D. R., & Kanuka, H. (2004). Blended learning: Uncovering its transformative potential in higher education. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 7(2), 95–105.
- Garrison, D. R., & Vaughan, N. D. (2008). *Blended learning in higher education: Framework, principles, and guidelines*. Jossey-Bass.

- Garrison, D. R., Anderson, T., & Archer, W. (2010). The community of inquiry framework: A synthesis of research and practice. *Journal of Asynchronous Learning Networks*, 14(1), 61–70.
- Githens, R. P. (2007). Best practices for managing student support services in distance education. *Distance Education*, 28(1), 65–86.
- Harris, J. M., & Rea, A. (2009). Technical support for distance learners: A case study. *Distance Education*, 30(2), 237–252.
- Harrison, D. (2013). Challenges of distance education: Lessons learned. *Distance Education*, 34(3), 372–390.
- Hattie, J., & Timperley, H. (2007). The power of feedback. *Review of Educational Research*, 77(1), 81–112.
- Hood, N., & Littlejohn, A. (2017). Exploring the factors that impact on the success of online distance education. *Journal of Learning Development in Higher Education*, 10(1), 112–130.
- Horton, W. (2011). *E-learning by design*. Wiley.
- Iruonagbe, T. I. (2016). The impact of open and distance learning in Nigeria. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 8(2), 30–37.
- Itasanmi, S. A., & Oni, M. T. (2019). Determinants of learners' satisfaction in open distance learning programmes in Nigeria. *Pakistan Journal of Distance and Online Learning*, 6(2), x-x.
- Kember, D. (1995). *Open learning courses for adults: A model of student progress*. Educational Technology Publications.
- Larsen, H., & Lewis, R. (2007). Cost-effectiveness in distance education: A case study. *Distance Education*, 28(1), 93–104.
- Lee, J. (2014). Online learners' satisfaction in distance education: A review of literature. *Educational Technology & Society*, 17(2), 26–36.
- Locke, E. A., & Latham, G. P. (2002). Building a practically useful theory of goal setting and task motivation: A 35-year odyssey. *American Psychologist*, 57(9), 705–717.
- McConnell, D. (2012). *Teaching in distance education: A framework for course design and evaluation*. Routledge.
- Moore, M. G., & Kearsley, G. (2011). *Distance education: A systems view of online learning* (3rd ed.). Wadsworth.
- Nicol, D. J., & Macfarlane-Dick, D. (2006). Formative assessment and self-regulated learning: A model and seven principles of good feedback practice. *Studies in Higher Education*, 31(2), 199–218.
- Norhayat, Z., Omar, N. B., Irda, S. K. A., & Farah, H. M. F. (2021). Factors affecting students' satisfaction and academic performance in Open & Distance Learning (ODL). *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 11(11), 1-16.
- Nunan, T., & Stubbins, M. (2005). The role of student support in distance education. *Distance Education*, 26(1), 47–68.
- Nwosu, F. A. (2017). The role of technology in open and distance learning in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 46(4), 469–487.
- Ogunyemi, M. (2007). Open and distance learning in Nigeria: The National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) experience. *The International Journal of Learning*, 14(1), 141–147.
- Olakulehin, F. K. (2007). Open and distance learning in Nigeria: A review of the National Open University of Nigeria. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 8(1), 1–9.
- O'Neill, P. (2012). Technical support services in distance education: A student perspective. *Journal of Distance Education*, 27(3), 57–70.
- Oyesomi, K., & Ogunlade, T. (2018). Open and distance learning in Nigeria: A review of the opportunities and challenges. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 9(17), 74–81.
- Palloff, R. M., & Pratt, K. (2013). *Lessons from the virtual classroom: The realities of online teaching*. Jossey-Bass.
- Perraton, H. (2000). *Open and distance learning in the developing world*. Routledge.
- Perry, L. M., Wirth, K. L., & Ziegler, S. A. (2012). Evaluating distance education programs: A comparison of four perspectives. *The Journal of Distance Education*, 27(1), 5–21.
- Raimi, L., & Adias, L. (2018). Collective bargaining: How useful is it for industrial harmony? Evidence from Shell Petroleum Development Company (SPDC), Port Harcourt, Rivers State. *Social Science and Law Journal of Policy Review & Development Strategies*, 6(1), 28–41.
- Schunk, D. H., Pintrich, P. R., & Meece, J. L. (2008). *Motivation and learning strategies for college success: A focus on self-regulated learning* (5th ed.). Pearson.

- Shah, M. (2018). Student satisfaction in online learning environments: A review of literature. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 32(5), 876–891.
- Simonson, M., Zvacek, S. M., & Smaldino, S. (2019). *Teaching and learning at a distance: Foundations of distance education* (7th ed.).
- Simpson, O. (2002). *Supporting students in open and distance learning*. Routledge.
- Swan, K. (2003). Learning effectiveness: What the research tells us. In M. G. Moore & W. Anderson (Eds.), *Handbook of distance education* (2nd ed., pp. 13–35). Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Tait, A. (2018). Education for development: From distance to open education. *Journal of Learning for Development*, 5(2), 101-115.
- Tinto, V. (1993). *Leaving college: Rethinking the causes and cures of student attrition*. University of Chicago Press.
- Tinto, V. (1997). Classrooms as communities: Exploring the educational character of student persistence. *Journal of Higher Education*, 68(6), 599–623.
- Tinto, V. (2012). *Leaving college: Rethinking the causes and cures of student attrition* (2nd ed.). University of Chicago Press.
- Vallerand, R. J., Pelletier, L. G., & Koestner, R. (1992). Motivation in education: The development of the academic motivation scale. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 52(4), 1003–1017.
- Vaughan, N. D. (2014). Student retention in online learning environments: A review of literature. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 11(1), 13–29.
- Zimmerman, B. J. (2000). Attaining self-regulation: A social cognitive perspective. In M. Boekaerts, P. R. Pintrich, & M. Zeidner (Eds.), *Handbook of self-regulation* (pp. 13–39). Academic Press.